

A STRUCTURAL EFFICIENCY STUDY OF ISOGRID-STIFFENED FIBER COMPOSITE LAMINATE SHELLS: BUCKLING AND POSTBUCKLING ANALYSES AND EXPERIMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in fiber composite manufacturing and structural efficiency requirements have led to the consideration of isogrid-stiffened fiber composite laminate shells for various aeronautical and space structural applications. Very little information, if any, on buckling and postbuckling of these grid-stiffened composite shells is currently available in the literature. In this paper, a combined analytical and experimental study is reported on buckling and postbuckling behavior of filament-wound fiber composite laminate cylindrical shells stiffened with isogrid structures made of the same composite. Buckling loads and postbuckling deformation characteristics of isogrid-stiffened composite shells, monocoque shells and pure composite isogrid stiffener structure have been obtained from linear bifurcation and geometric nonlinear postbuckling analyses and experiments.

INTRODUCTION

The current design of high-performance aircraft places a strong emphasis on structural efficiency and minimum weight. The most common practice in weight reduction is utilization of thin stiffened composite plate and shell type structures. The stiffeners are usually stringers and frames or ribs which are structurally attached orthogonal to the stringers. While such stiffened components are structurally efficient, the cost of fabrication and assemblage makes them expensive. An alternative is the introduction of integrated fiber-composite isogrids in which the stiffening composite elements are fabricated simultaneously with the fiber composite shell structures with a pattern of repetitive equilateral triangles. Among the advantages of the integrated isogrid-stiffened structures are: (1). inherently stable configuration [1], (2). comparatively low production costs, and (3) demonstrated structural efficiency.

Advances in the manufacturing technology of composite materials and structures have led to the development of highly efficient integrated grid-stiffened fiber composite laminate shells. A monocoque fiber composite shell and stiffeners are generally fabricated by a filament winding or resin infusion molding technique and subsequently co-cured to form an integrated stiffened composite shell. The automated process offers enormous potential for low-cost, high-speed production of aircraft structural components due to their cost effectiveness and the high quality of the end product expected. In addition, the integrated fabrication process is expected to reduce the

delamination failure of the stiffeners when the stiffened fiber composite components are subjected to loads. Widespread applicability of these composite laminate structures warrants a thorough understanding of their stability related-deformations and load-carrying capability.

It is recognized that buckling loads and postbuckling characteristics of stiffened cylindrical shells depend on complex interactions among shell materials, geometric imperfections and local and overall shell buckling modes [2]. Several studies have been reported [1,3-4] on compressive buckling and dynamic characteristics of the isogrid structural concept and grid-stiffened composite panels. Structural analysis and design optimization of a geodesically stiffened wing-rib panel have been conducted [5]. Among the recent analytical and experimental research conducted are stability of stiffened composite laminate shells [6] and panels [7]. An analytical study has also been reported [8] on effects of stiffness discontinuities and selected structural induced damage on grid-stiffened composite laminate panels.

The objectives of this paper are to: (1). develop an accurate analytical model to study buckling and postbuckling of integrated isogrid-stiffened fiber-composite cylindrical shells subjected to axial compression; (2). determine from experiments the buckling load, postbuckling deformation and mode shapes, and compare them with solutions obtained from analyses; and (3). evaluate structural efficiency of isogrid-stiffened fiber composite shells by comparing the results with those obtained for monocoque fiber composite shells and pure isogrid structures subjected to the same loading.

In the next section, fabrication of stiffened and monocoque fiber composite laminate cylindrical shells is summarized. Finite-element models used for the linear bifurcation and the geometrically nonlinear postbuckling analyses are outlined. Details of experiments, including experimental set-up and procedures and data acquisition and analysis, are described subsequently. Finally, numerical and experimental results are reported for the stiffened and monocoque composite shells as well as for the corresponding pure composite isogrid structures.

FABRICATION OF ISOGRID-STIFFENED AND MONOCOQUE COMPOSITE LAMINATE SHELLS AND PURE COMPOSITE ISOGRID STRUCTURES

The fiber composite shell structures considered were made of AS4 fibers and the Shell 9405/9470 epoxy polymer. Smooth monocoque composite shells were wet-wound with application of the resin to the tow using a standard filament winding technique. The integrated grid rib/shell were fabricated with a special dual-head winder that allowed simultaneous applications of grid rib and shell fibers to the mandrel. This special winder is not shown, owing to space limitations. One head operated on each side of the machine, allowing operations of both heads on different fiber winding patterns. The +/- 60° grids were applied by one head while the +/-30° and 90° shell plies were applied by the other. Thus, the grids and shell plies were integrated with one another. The shell plies were wound in the same way as the monocoque shells and the grids were formed by B-staged tow formed earlier by wet winding and heating. The wet parts were cured in a vacuum bag in an autoclave by a standard process suitable for the resin.

Four types of composite shell constructions were filament wound for testing and analysis: thick-shell, thin-shell, isogrid-stiffened thin shell, and pure composite isogrid structure of the same geometry. Geometric parameters of these composite structures are given in Table 1. A photograph of these structures is shown in Fig. 1. Notice that the thick composite shell was made on an equal-weight basis with the isogrid-stiffened thin composite shell. Also, the base thin shell of the isogrid-stiffened composite shell was identical in construction to the thin monocoque composite shell.

METHODS OF ANALYSIS

The monocoque composite laminate cylindrical shell considered is shown in Fig. 2 with length L , and a $[\Theta_1/\Theta_2.../\Theta_n]$ n-ply lay-up. The geometry of the integrated stiffened composite shell is depicted in Fig. 3. Based on orientations of their longitudinal axes, the composite stiffeners stiffeners may be classified into two types: lateral and axial. The longitudinal axes of the laterals are

inclined to the cylindrical axis, and are segments of left- and right-handed circular helices (with helical angle $\phi=60^\circ$ with respect to the cylindrical axis). Joined to them are the axials, with axes parallel to the cylindrical axis. The junction nodes of the laterals and axials have circumferential and axial dimensions l and m (Fig. 2) and lay-up $[\phi/0^\circ/-\phi]$. The cross section of the fiber isogrid element (Fig. 3) is modeled as a semi-ellipse with the major axis b and thickness t_b .

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES

Eight-node isoparametric thin shell elements with five degrees of freedom per node are used for discretization of the monocoque composite shell and the composite laminate wall of the grid stiffened shells. These elements are C^0 continuous, with Mindlin-type displacement-field assumptions. Three-node beam elements with quadratic interpolation functions are used to model the stiffeners. The isogrid junction nodes are modeled by eight-node thick-shell elements [9].

Buckling and Postbuckling Analyses

Buckling and postbuckling analyses of both stiffened and unstiffened fiber-composite laminate shells with geometric imperfections are carried out, using an ABAQUS [10] finite element code. The buckling load, $(P_x)_{cr}$, is obtained from a linear bifurcation analysis [10]. In order to construct the path from prebuckling to postbuckling equilibrium states, a geometric imperfection is introduced to the initial geometry of the composite shell as

$$\{I\} = \{O\} + \epsilon t \{\psi\} \quad (1)$$

where $\{I\}$ are the resulting nodal coordinates of the structure with the imperfections; $\{O\}$, the nodal coordinates of the structure without any imperfection; ϵ is a scaling coefficient; t is the thickness of the laminate shell wall; and $\{\psi\}$ is the eigenmode obtained from the bifurcation analysis corresponding to $(P_x)_{cr}$.

The kinematic relationship involving large displacements and small strains is used in conjunction with an updated Lagrangian formulation. A modified Riks' nonlinear algorithm, implemented in the ABAQUS [10], is used for the geometric nonlinear postbuckling analysis. A systematic study has been carried out, using the aforementioned bifurcation analysis, to evaluate the effect of mesh discretization on buckling loads and buckling modes of monocoque composite laminate shells [9]. The meshes obtained for the converged solutions are used for subsequent postbuckling analyses of monocoque and isogrid-stiffened composite laminate shells with imperfections.

BUCKLING AND POSTBUCKLING EXPERIMENTS

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Axial compression experiments were conducted to characterize and compare the load-bearing strengths and stability characteristics of the composite shells. Specimens were cut to a predetermined length and squared off at the ends. Two end fixtures were made from 2.54 cm (1") thick aluminum plates. A 15.24 cm (6") diameter, 1.27 cm (0.5") deep groove was machined into each plate. The shell ends were inserted in the grooves of the end fixtures and potted with a low melting-point alloy. Strain gages were mounted at the mid-section of the test sections and LVDT's were installed between the two end fixtures. The loading machine was a 889.64 KN (200 kip) servo-hydraulic test frame. A floating platen was mounted on the actuator to support the specimen-fixture assembly. Load, actuator displacement, as well as strain gage and LVDT readings were recorded by a data acquisition system. The test events were recorded on a VCR system for later review. In Fig. 4 the experimental setup is shown for illustration.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Since the four types of composite shells and isogrid structures were of very different constructions, distinct stability characteristics under axial compression were expected. Two specimen lengths, 20.32 cm (8") and 60.96 cm (24"), were selected for use in most of the experiments. Only the tests conducted on the 20.32 cm (8") long specimens are reported here due to space limitations.

Multiple test runs were conducted on each specimen. Initially, the specimens were subjected to small load magnitudes; say, 2.22-8.89 KN (500-2000 lbs), depending on the type of the composite shells, to eliminate backlashes in the test link and to condition or calibrate the instruments. This was followed by a key test run which was carried out to the point when some form of failure was observed. In some cases, this key test run was allowed to continue to some point beyond the failure load to monitor the process of damage propagation or postbuckling deformation behavior. In other cases, the specimens were unloaded from the key test runs at failure loads and restarted in a new test run to check for any permanent damage to the specimens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

First, experimental results are reported here on the axial compressive behavior of the four different types of composite shells. The load-displacement curves of key test runs for the specimens are given in Fig. 5.

Thick composite laminate shells

The thick composite shells failed catastrophically at the mid-section with damage being observed all around the circumference of the shells. The failure mode was fiber-dominated fracture under compression in the ply direction as shown in Fig. 6.

Thin composite laminate shells

The thin composite shells buckled under axial compression. As shown in Fig. 7, the region where instability occurred was very localized and bounded by the diamond-shape $\pm 30^\circ$ winding patterns within three to four ply width. (The width of the ply was about 1.27 cm (0.5")). Further compression on the specimens resulted in increasing the number of these localized buckling zones. Within the buckled area, especially around its edges, ply delamination and ply splitting started to occur. Very few fiber or ply fracture were observed within the limited extent of compression in the experiments.

Isogrid-stiffened thin composite shells.

Global instability was not observed in the axial compression of the isogrid-stiffened thin composite shells. Failure occurred in a rapid sequence with multiple events at localized areas bounded by unit cells of the isogrid pattern. The process proceeded with: (1) fracture of the axial grid stiffeners in the unit cells and, (2) immediate local buckling of the thin shell inside the diamond shape unit cells bounded by the $\pm 60^\circ$ grids, (3) further compression resulted in ply splitting, delamination and fracture. Fig. 8 gives a typical failure mode in the isogrid-stiffened thin composite shell.

Pure composite isogrid structures

The deformation and failure processes in pure isogrid structures made of the fiber composite were similar to those that may occur in typical truss structures. First, the compressive force caused bending in a increasing number of axial grids as the test proceeded. This resulted in leveling the compressive load with an increase in deformation. The deformed grids with the unidirectional fiber composite would eventually delaminate and lose their load bearing capability. Sudden load drops

occurred when the majority of the axial grids were lost at some fixed axial positions along the structure. The $\pm 60^\circ$ grids began to share more loads. Because of the twisting moment in these angled grids, node separations and fracture were observed at very large compressive deformations. Typical failure of a pure graphite/epoxy isogrid structure is shown in Fig. 9.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linear bifurcation and geometric nonlinear postbuckling analyses are carried out for the aforementioned isogrid-stiffened and monocoque fiber-composite laminate shells as well as the pure composite isogrid structures of the same geometry. One end of the shell is fixed and the other end undergoes a uniform axial displacement, when subjected to axial compression. The geometric dimensions of the cylindrical shell are: $L=20.32$ cm (8.0"), $D=13.97$ cm (5.5"), and the composite laminate lay-up is $[(\pm 30^\circ)/90^\circ]$. The geometry of the stiffening isogrid elements are: $t_b = 0.20$ cm (0.08"), $b_{axial} = 0.79$ cm (0.31"), $b_{lateral} = 1.04$ cm (0.41"), $l = 0.46$ cm (0.37"), $m = b_{axial}$. Elastic properties of the unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite are: $E_{11} = 138$ GPa (20 Mpsi), $E_{22} = 14.47$ GPa (2.1 Mpsi), $G_{12} = G_{13} = 7.10$ GPa (1.03 Mpsi), $\nu = 0.3$, and $G_{23} = 5.38$ GPa (0.78 Mpsi). The imperfection geometry introduced in the postbuckling analysis is scaled to $0.001t$, i.e. $\epsilon=0.001$. In the figures described in this section, the displacements are normalized with respect to the shell wall thickness t , and the applied loads are normalized with respect to the reference bifurcation load $(P_x)_{cr}$.

Cylindrical Monocoque $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]$ Composite Shells with $t = 0.053$ cm (0.0210")

The bifurcation load of the monocoque composite shell is obtained as $(P_x)_{cr} = 29.67$ KN (6.67 kip). Results of the end-shortening vs. the applied load of the monocoque composite shell are presented in Fig. 10(a). The shell exhibits a linear load-displacement relationship in the prebuckling region. The postbuckling path of the monocoque composite shell is rather unstable. In order to illustrate the numerical characteristics of instability of the postbuckling path, different parts of the path have been shifted in Fig. 10(b). Note that the deformation at failure, observed from the experiment, compares well with that from the computed postbuckling failure (Fig. 11).

Cylindrical Monocoque $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]$ Composite Shells with $t = 0.113$ cm (0.0447")

The effect of the shell thickness on buckling and postbuckling characteristics is studied. A two-fold increase in thickness results in a four fold increase in the bifurcation load $(P_x)_{cr} = 131.31$ KN (29.52 kip). Numerical results of the end-shortening vs. applied load are presented in Fig. 12. The postbuckling deformations are not localized, but run around the circumference of the shell (Fig. 13). This is consistent with the observed failure mode of the shell in the experiments.

Isogrid-stiffened $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]_S$ Composite Cylindrical Shells

The bifurcation load of this isogrid-stiffened composite shell is found to be $(P_x)_{cr} = 60.81$ KN (13.67 kip), which is twice that of the monocoque composite shell with the same lay-up and geometry. Solutions for the end-shortening vs. applied load of the stiffened composite shell are presented in Fig. 14. The shell exhibits a linear load-displacement relationship in the prebuckling region. The postbuckling path, however, is unstable. The lowest postbuckling load obtained is $0.79(P_x)_{cr}$. The postbuckling deformations (Fig. 15) of the stiffened composite shell are characterized by a localized failure mode.

Pure Composite Isogrid Structures

The bifurcation load of a pure composite isogrid structure is found to be $(P_x)_{cr} = 17.97$ KN (4.04 kip), lower than those of the corresponding isogrid-stiffened and monocoque shells. As compared to the stiffened composite shell, the predicted end-shortening vs. applied-load relationship for the pure composite isogrid structure (Fig. 16) has a nonlinear prebuckling load-displacement path. Numerical results for the deformation of the pure isogrid structure in the postbuckling region are depicted in Fig. 17. The buckling load obtained from experiment ($P_{buck} \sim 11.12$ KN (2.5 kip)) is of similar magnitude as the bifurcation load obtained from the analysis. Furthermore, the end-shortening vs. applied-load relationship obtained from the experiment is nonlinear.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the solutions of the analyses conducted and the experimental results obtained in this study, the following conclusions may be drawn:

1. Continuous filament-wound composite isogrid stiffeners significantly increase the bifurcation load of an isogrid-stiffened fiber-composite laminate shell, as compared to that of the corresponding monocoque shell.
2. Solutions for buckling loads and postbuckling deformations of the monocoque and stiffened composite shells and the pure composite isogrid structures compare well with the experimental results.
3. The buckling strength of a pure composite isogrid structure is significantly lower than either of the corresponding monocoque or the isogrid-stiffened shell of the same geometry.
4. The fiber composite structures manufactured on an equal weight basis depict similar load bearing capacity.
5. Local deformations predicted and observed during postbuckling of the stiffened shells underline their imperfection sensitivity.

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Table 1. Geometry of Integrated Isogrid Stiffened Composite Shells

Structure Type	Diameter D (cm)	Shell Thickness t (cm)	Rib+Shell Thickness (cm)	Linear Weight (KN/m)
Thick shell	15.24	0.102	-	7.20
Thin-shell	15.24	0.058	-	3.63
Isogrid Stiffened shell	15.24	0.058	0.173-0.188	7.14
Isogrid rib only	15.24	-	0.152-0.198	3.86

Fig. 1 Four types of monocoque and isogrid-stiffened composite laminate shells and pure composite isogrid structure

Fig. 4 Experimental setup

(a) Geometry and coordinates of monocoque composite shell

(b) Laminate lay-up

Fig. 2. Geometry, laminate lay-up and coordinates of a monocoque fiber-composite laminate shell

Fig. 3 Geometry of isogrid stiffeners and a grid intersection in a stiffened fiber-composite laminate cylindrical shell

Fig. 5. End-shortening vs. applied load for graphite/epoxy composite laminate cylindrical shells obtained from experiments

Fig. 6. Compression failure of graphite/epoxy thick composite laminate shell

Fig. 7. Compression failure of the graphite/epoxy thin composite laminate shell

Fig. 8. Compression failure of isogrid stiffened graphite/epoxy composite laminate shell

Fig. 9. Compression failure of a pure graphite/epoxy isogrid structure

Fig. 11. Postbuckling of a monocoque $[(\pm 30)/(90)]$ graphite/epoxy shell subjected to axial compression

Fig. 10. End-shortening vs. applied load for monocone $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]$ graphite/epoxy laminate shell with imperfection subjected to axial compression ($t=0.02''$)

Fig. 12 End-shortening vs. applied load for monocone $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]$ graphite/epoxy shell with imperfection subjected to axial compression ($t=0.045''$)

Fig. 13 Postbuckling deformation of a monocone $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]$ graphite/epoxy shell subjected to axial compression ($t=0.045''$)

Fig. 14. End-shortening vs. applied load for isogrid-stiffened $[(\pm 30^\circ)/(90^\circ)]_S$ shell with imperfection subjected to axial compression

Fig. 16. End-shortening vs. applied load for the pure graphite/epoxy isogrid structure with imperfection subjected to axial compression

Fig. 17 Postbuckling deformation of a pure graphite/epoxy isogrid structure subjected to axial compression

Fig. 15 Postbuckling deformation of an isogrid-stiffened [(±30°)/(90°)]S graphite/epoxy shell subjected to axial compression